

USER AWARENESS AND TRAINING ON E-RESOURCES: AWARENESS LEVELS AMONG STUDENTS AND FACULTY

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ABSTRACT

The extensive growth of electronic resources in the academic libraries has resulted in dramatic changes to the academic libraries. In order for the users to effectively use the e-resources, the academic library users must first be aware of the e-resources and have to undergo some type of training on how to use the e-resources. The current study investigates that the level of the awareness, frequency and use and the type of training on how to use the e-resources. The current examines the awareness levels of the students and faculty members regarding e-resources in academic institutions. The study also evaluates the impact of the library orientation programs, information literacy, training programs and how these factors impact on the ability of the users to access the electronic information resources and its effective use. Overall results from the study indicate that providing structured user education programs will contribute to increase user awareness, user confidence and ultimately increase the research productivity amongst the academic community

KEYWORDS: *E-Resources, User Awareness, Information Literacy, Faculty and Students.*

Article History

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INTRODUCTION

Academic libraries have been shifted from traditional print collections to the digital platforms, subscribing to various online databases, e-journals, e-books, institutional repositories, and open access resources. Despite of the availability of rich digital collections, utilization depends on the user's awareness, digital literacy skills and familiarity with search strategies. However, the user awareness and training play a crucial role in bridging the gap between availability and effective usage.

The programs for improving the awareness and providing training are therefore crucial to closing gap between the availability of the resources and their effective use. Teaching, research, accreditation requirements and scholarly publishing, the students and faculty in the academic institutions are depending more and more on the digital resources.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Previous studies indicate that faculty members generally exhibit higher awareness and utilization of e-resources when compared to students. Research highlights that awareness does not automatically translate into effective use unless supported by the structured training programs.

The review of existing studies clearly indicates that:

- The faculty generally exhibit higher awareness and usage of e-resources than students
- Student awareness requires structured training
- User education programs significantly enhance effective utilization
- Institutional support and continuous training are essential for maximizing investment on e-resources.

RESEARCH GAP

A review of existing literature reveals that numerous studies have examined the usage patterns of e-resources in the academic institutions. However, several gaps remain are as follows:

- Limited comparative analysis
- Lack of focus on awareness vs usage
- Insufficient evaluation of training impact
- Engineering-Specific context underexplored
- Digital Literacy integration gap

These gaps indicate the need for the systematic study assessing awareness and training effectiveness among both students and faculty, particularly in the engineering colleges. Despite of the investments towards subscribing to electronic resources such as e-journals, e-books and research databases and many other resources suggest lack of awareness, inadequate training and insufficient information literacy skills.

The study seeks to examine user awareness and training on e-resources, with special emphasis on comparing awareness levels among students and faculty.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

- To assess the level of awareness of available e-resources among students and faculty.
- To identify the types of e-resources frequently used
- To compare awareness levels between students and faculty
- To identify the challenges faced in accessing and using e-resources
- To suggest measures for improvement
- To suggest measures for improvement

METHODOLOGY

The study adopts a descriptive and analytical research design based on the secondary data. The study rely on previously published scholarly works, institutional reports and statistical data related to user awareness and training programs on e-resources.

Secondary data refers to data that has already been collected, analyzed and published by other researchers or other institutions.

Data were collected from:

- Peer-reviewed journal article
- Conference proceedings
- Academic these and dissertations
- Library usage statistics
- Open access research Journals
- Google scholar
- Shodhganga

The advantages of the secondary data methodology were:

- Cost effective
- Time-efficient
- Access to large scale studies
- Provides historical and trend-based insights

The secondary data methodology provides a comprehensive understanding of user awareness and training on e-resources by synthesizing existing research findings.

SCOPE OF THE STUDY

- Limited to students and faculty of engineering college
- Focus on awareness and training related to subscribed and open access resources
- To examine the usage patterns and challenges

RESULTS AND FINDINGS

The analysis is based on a review of recent scholarly articles, institutional reports and conference papers published between 2018 and 2025. The reviewed studies focus on

- Awareness levels of e-resources
- Usage patterns among students and faculty
- Role of libraries in promoting e-resources

The secondary data indicate that the faculty members exhibit high awareness of subscribed databases, e-resources were as the students show lower awareness particularly regarding specialized databases and institutional repositories.

The awareness of Open Access (OA) resources is increasing but remains unused. Several studies reported that the faculty awareness levels ranged between 70% to 90% whereas the students ranged between 40% to 65%. Lower awareness among students suggests the orientation programs or limited to e-resource training programs.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study concludes that awareness and training are critical determinants of effective e-resource utilization in engineering institutions. While the faculty members demonstrate relatively higher awareness, students require structured and continuous training programs and must integrate information literacy into the curriculum to ensure the maximum utilization of the e-resources.

RECOMMENDATION ARE AS FOLLOWS

- Conduct mandatory orientation programs for the first-year students
- Provide online tutorials and recorded training sessions
- Encourage faculty-library collaboration
- Improve remote access infrastructure

REFERENCES

1. Acanit, M., Ngulube, P., & Mojapelo, S. M. (2024). *Factors influencing the use of e-library resources by postgraduate engineering students at Kyambogo University in Uganda. Information Development. Advance online publication. https://doi.org/10.1177/02666669241291566*
2. Baayel, P., & Asante, E. (2019). *Students' awareness and use of electronic information resources: A study of Koforidua Technical University. International Journal of Social Media and Interactive Learning Environments, 2(6), 122–136. https://doi.org/10.1504/IJSMILE.2019.102164*
3. He, D., Wu, D., Yue, Z., Fu, A., & Vo, K. T. (2012). *Undergraduate students' interaction with online information resources in their academic tasks: A comparative study. Aslib Proceedings: New Information Perspectives, 64(6), 615–640. https://doi.org/10.1108/00012531211281715*
4. Nicholas, D., Clark, D., & Rowlands, I. (2009). *Online use and information seeking behaviour: Institutional and subject comparisons of UK researchers. Journal of Information Science, 35(6), 660–676. https://doi.org/10.1177/0165551509338341*
5. Palani, R., & Ramesh Babu, V. (2019). *Electronic resources access pattern in engineering college libraries: An analytical study at Vellore District, Tamil Nadu. Asian Journal of Information Science and Technology, 9(2), 56–62.*
6. Reddy, A. H. P., & Reddy, V. P. (2019). *Use of e-sources by the students of Acharya Nagarjuna University Engineering College: A survey. International Journal of Information Dissemination and Technology, 9(4). * https://doi.org/10.5958/2249-5576.2019.00035.9*
7. Shigwedha, J. J. O. N. (2020). *Access and use of electronic resources by the students at the selected campuses of the University of Namibia (Doctoral dissertation). ProQuest Dissertations & Theses Global.*